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Registered

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5 November 2024

Renewal date

5 November 2029

Overview

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5 November 2024

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11 November 2024

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12 November 2024

Indication of Product

WEARABLE DISASTER EMERGENCY COMMUNICATION DEVICE

Classification

Class	10 - CLOCKS AND WATCHES AND OTHER MEASURING INSTRUMENTS, CHECKING AND SIGNALLING INSTRUMENTS
Sub class	05 - INSTRUMENTS, APPARATUS AND DEVICES FOR CHECKING, SECURITY OR TESTING
Class	29 - DEVICES AND EQUIPMENT AGAINST FIRE HAZARDS, FOR ACCIDENT PREVENTION AND FOR RESCUE
Sub class	02 - DEVICES AND EQUIPMENT FOR ACCIDENT PREVENTION AND FOR RESCUE, NOT ELSEWHERE SPECIFIED

Illustrations

Disclaimer

No claim is made for the colour shown

Designs

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History

No history is available for this design